

Microeconomic Analysis of Fisheries and Aquaculture in Oman

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Academic Year: 2025-2026

Submission Date: May 2026

Executive Summary

This research focuses on Oman's fisheries and aquaculture sector, examining market structure, the effectiveness of pricing models, and the economics of increasing export income and enhancing national food security using microeconomics theory in relation to empirical data from the "Fisheries Statistics book 2024" and other sources. The analysis reveals the coexistence of two subsystems: an oligopoly in the aquaculture and commercial fishing industries and perfect competition in artisanal fishing, which accounts for 77% of the industry. The results reveal that while total production has grown to 900,630 tons, the level of production dropped to 27 thousand tons because of powerful summer seasonal shocks. Although the aggregate demand is very elastic, there is an inherent structural inelasticity in the demand for some fish, such as Kingfish. Government measures address the "tragedy of the commons" by restricting exports and imposing fishing bans. The study recommends the strengthening of cold storages within the region to manage seasonal prices fluctuations, the use of adaptive licensing and quotas to prevent biomass exploitation, and local fish feed production through the Khazaen plant to ensure a sustainable fisheries industry.

Keywords: Fisheries, Aquaculture, Microeconomics theory, Production, Structure, Demand, Shocks, Elasticity, Prices, Government, Exploitation, Tragedy of Common.

JEL Classification: Q22, Q18, D12, D40

Introduction

Industry Overview

The fish industry in the Sultanate of Oman forms a traditional culture as well as the economy of the country. World Bank sources state that the fishing and agricultural sectors employed around 80% of the population before the discovery of oil in the 1960s (World Bank, 2015). The country enjoys certain geographical advantages, such as being located by three seas, namely, the Arabian Sea, the Sea of Oman, and the Arabian Gulf. Such a geographical location provides extensive marine biodiversity owing to a long coastline of 3,165 kilometers (FAO, 2019).

Currently, the fishing industry has been ranked second in terms of natural resources following oil and gas (World Bank, 2015). It has become a key aspect of Oman Vision 2040 in order to increase economic diversification. Statistics of the Fisheries Statistics Yearbook of 2023 shows that fish production has grown significantly, reaching from 553,445 tons in 2018 to 793,771 tons in 2023 with a CAGR of 7.5% and 900,630 tons in 2024. fish production value more than doubled during this period, reaching up to OMR 531 million in 2023 from OMR 269 million in 2018.

Figure 1: Total Fisheries Production and its Value (1985-2024)

Source: Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Water Resources. (2024). *Fishery statistics book 2024* (Issue No. 2). Directorate General of Planning, Statistics Department.

As regards the structure of production, the Yearbook on Fisheries statistics reveals that artisanal fishing is the most prevalent, and it provides the bedrock of the sector by providing 77% of total production in 2024. Commercial fishing experienced notable growth to contribute around 7%, while coastal fishing and aquaculture made up 15% and 1%, respectively.

Figure 2: Fisheries Production Depends on Sectors (2024)

Source: Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Water Resources. (2024). *Fishery statistics book 2024* (Issue No. 2). Directorate General of Planning, Statistics Department.

The aquaculture industry forms an integral part of Oman’s diversification plan as stipulated in Vision 2040, and it plays an important role in boosting food security by lowering reliance on the unpredictable natural fisheries resources (MAFWR, 2024; World Bank, 2015). The industry has seen marked improvement in terms of its qualitative nature, producing a total output of 5,507 tons in 2024, driven by a strong financial backbone valued at over OMR 400 million (Al Alawi, 2026; MAFWR, 2024). The current operations are geared towards producing high-value commercial species such as shrimps, cobias, and tilapia, thanks to suitable environmental settings and advanced technologies like floating cage and RAS systems (MAFWR, 2024; Mishrif, 2024).

With regards to geography, there are governorates where most production occurs. The governorate of Al Wusta takes the lead at 33% of artisanal fishing production, followed by the governorate of South Sharqiyah at 31%, and then the governorate of Dhofar at 13% (MAFWR, 2024). This geographical distribution brings up many economic implications regarding logistics and transportation to central locations and ports for export.

Concerning food security, Oman reached a very high level of self-sufficiency, ranging between 146% as reported by the Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Water Resources

in 2024. Such surplus has boosted Oman’s position in international markets, as about 37% of its total production is exported to about 84 countries around the world (*Fisheries Statistics Book 2024*).

Figure 3: Fisheries Exports (2024)

Source: Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Water Resources. (2024). *Fishery statistics book 2024* (Issue No. 2). Directorate General of Planning, Statistics Department.

Research Purpose

This project aims to study the fisheries and aquaculture sector in terms of microeconomics perspectives. The focus is on understanding the dynamics of different price systems and the competition that exists within this sector. Another topic covered by the paper is the effect of international business activities, policies and regulations on market performance and on the equilibrium between supply and demand. To conduct an adequate analysis of these issues and present relevant conclusions on the topic, the study utilizes appropriate statistics and economic concepts.

Research Questions

1. What is the market structure of the fisheries and aquaculture sector?
2. What is the pricing mechanism used in that market?
3. To what extent do government policies contribute
4. Is aquaculture a viable solution to ensure a stable supply?

Data & Methodology

This study adopts a descriptive analytical approach, relying on secondary sources to ensure data quality and reliability. Data was drawn from reputable governmental and international institutions. Microeconomic principles formed the cornerstone for analyzing market structure, supply and demand, and elasticity. These tools allowed for the fisheries and aquaculture sector in Oman, its pricing mechanisms, and the role of government intervention.

Reliable and up-to-date secondary sources were used to obtain data on total annual landings, fishing and boat licenses, exports, etc. These sources included:

- Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Water Resources
The primary source of data on the fisheries sector, including the volume and value of production (artisanal, coastal, and commercial fishing), the volume of new and renewed licenses, as published in the 2023 and 2024 fisheries Statistical Yearbook. Information was also provided on key projects implemented to support the sector.
- The National Centre for Statistics and Information (NCSI)
It provided information on the sector, including total production by fishing methods and fish species, the value of production, the quantity and value of exports, and renewed and new licenses, as published in the Statistical Yearbook 2025. It also obtained fish prices by species in the markets between 2017 and 2024.

- The FAO and World Bank
They provided information on the fisheries and aquaculture profile in Oman and an overview of national aquaculture, including information on efforts undertaken, major projects, types of fish farmed, total production, sector promotion and management, challenges, and development plans.
- Oman Vision 2040 and Fisheries Development Oman Group
This section outlined the objectives and key projects planned to support the development and sustainability of the fisheries and aquaculture sectors.
- Academic Research
Research studies from the Journal of Agriculture and Marine Sciences on Market efficiency and sustainability practices were consulted. Additionally, research from the Springer journal on fisheries trends and indicators for the period 1985-2022 was also conferred.

Data collection and measurement units

The collected data covered the period from 1985 to 2024, providing a comprehensive timeline of changes and trends in the fisheries and aquaculture sector. Production, export, and import data collected from governmental and international sources are expressed in tons and their values in Omani Rials to facilitate tracking. The market structure was categorized according to the number of fishers vendors in the market, the pricing mechanism for products, and the ease of entry and exit from the market. To assess the elasticity, market prices were compared with supply, demand, and export rates. The role of government intervention in market management and the maintenance of sustainable fish stocks was highlighted. Data triangulation was used in some instances to ensure consistency and reliability of the results by comparing data from different sources. This systematic approach provides a clear picture and oversight of the fisheries and aquaculture sector in Oman over time.

Industry Analysis

Market Structure

The fisheries market in Oman has a dualistic framework with a segmented structure where two different economic models run concurrently. The biggest segment of artisanal fishing is considered to be a market model of perfect competition since it has an abundant supply of producers, with 60 thousand fishers who work independently and guarantee fresh supplies of goods (Fisheries Statistics Book 2024). In such conditions, fishers are the price takers in the segment, while the price for fish is formed through direct supply-demand interactions within landing halls or digital auction bidding on Bahar (WTO, 2023: (*Behar Market*, n.d.)). The traditional segment accounts for 77% of total fish production in the Sultanate, thus becoming one of the sources of food security in the country (MAFWR, 2024; Mishrif, 2024).

At the same time, the commercial fishing and aquaculture market is prone to the feature of oligopoly. Indeed, it involves only a few powerful companies dominating both in production and sales, such as FDO and its subsidiaries, which are regarded as the leaders (FDO, 2022; Mishrif, 2024). This market has many obstacles to a new company's emergence; it requires a huge initial government investment of up to OMR 400 million in the aquaculture subsector and the use of advanced technologies such as industrial fishing vessels, floating aquaculture tanks, and even satellites (VMS) (Al Alawi, 2026; FDO, 2022). The production volume in this market segment does not exceed 9% of the total production (8% is produced due to commercial fishing, while 1% is related to aquaculture), yet it is primarily focused on adding maximum value to products and exporting them (MAFWR, 2024).

Figure 4: Total Fisheries Production of Commercial fishing and Number of Boats Used (1994-2024)

Source: Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Water Resources. (2024). *Fishery statistics book 2024* (Issue No. 2). Directorate General of Planning, Statistics Department.

Figure 5: Number of New and Renewed Fishing Licenses (2024)

Source: Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Water Resources. (2024). *Fishery statistics book 2024* (Issue No. 2). Directorate General of Planning, Statistics Department.

Supply and demand

The Sultanate of Oman recorded considerable growth in the fisheries supply chain, which is characterized by seasonality in operations. Overall, there has been a 13.5% rise in fish production from 793,771 tons in 2023 to 900,630 tons in 2024 (Fisheries Statistics Book, 2024). Despite such growth, the supply curve experiences some shocks due to climatic factors such as the monsoon winds that cause movement to the left of the supply curve by 43.6% in July compared to the period of maximum abundance. Such movement causes increases in local equilibrium price levels because of the scarcity of pelagic and demersal fish species (MAFWR, 2024; Mishrif, 2024).

On the other hand, the domestic consumption demand in 2024 showed a significant increase in consumption level. The quantity available for domestic consumption has increased to 602,077 tons from 495,311 tons, hence increasing the consumption level per capita annually from 53.6 kg to 80 kg (MAFWR, 2024). The total demand is shared among three beneficiaries, including:

- Human consumption demand, where fish is seen as one of the indispensable sources of protein.
- Intensive industrial demand, which refers to the demand from fish oil and fish meal factories. In 2024, about 180 thousand tons of anchovies were processed to achieve maximum added value.
- External demand accounts for 37% of total production volume, exported to 84 nations.

Figure 6: Fisheries Production, Available for Consumption, and Per Capita (2003-2024)

Source: Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Water Resources. (2024). *Fishery statistics book 2024* (Issue No. 2). Directorate General of Planning, Statistics Department.

Fish Group	Quantity (tons)	Quantity Growth	Value (thousand rials)	Value Growth	Share of Total Production
Large Pelagic Fish	203,110	15%	196,239	-4%	29%
Small Pelagic Fish	346,434	-8%	105,574	20%	50%
Demersal Fish	118,504	6%	79,948	-1%	17%
Sharks	9,219	47%	7,317	12%	1%
Crustaceans & Mollusks	10,816	-63%	24,592	-55%	2%
Unknown	4,890	-25%	4,528	-24%	1%
Total	692,973	-2%	418,197	-5%	100%

Table 1: Catch by fish group (Artisanal Fishing)

Source: Ministry of Agriculture, Fisheries and Water Resources. (2024). *Fishery statistics book 2024* (Issue No. 2). Directorate General of Planning, Statistics Department.

Elasticity

Since fish is one of the primary proteins consumed by Omani society, domestic demand for it is relatively inelastic (FAO, 2019; Al-Abri et al., 2009). However, when the arc elasticity is used to measure the price elasticity of demand for the period 2023-2024, there emerges the indication of significant responsiveness. Particularly, the mean price per kilogram went down from OMR 0.670 in 2023 to 0.644 in 2024 (3.9%), with the corresponding increase in the domestic quantity of goods required by about 17.7%. Hence, the elasticity coefficient equals approximately -4.5. The magnitude of elasticity is greater than one, demonstrating that the general demand in the abundant year 2024 is elastic. Meaning that the price drop induces people to make more purchases in proportionally higher quantities than the fall in price. The excitement and willingness to buy fish as an alternative to meat when the prices are affordable. Nevertheless, there is variation in price elasticity regarding certain types of seafood. The consumption of staple foods like jeedher and sahwa is not highly sensitive because of their constant need and the fact that they form part of the Omani food system. On the other hand, products such as sharkha and shrimp are highly elastic in terms of pricing.

Pricing Mechanism

Omani fish market pricing operates through an evolving economic process where supply and demand are reflected immediately. The auction system is characterized by the exchange between the fisherman and purchaser in fish landing sites and wholesalers, where open bidding occurs to establish the price of the product following weighing (WTO, 2023; MAFWR, 2024). The invention of the “Behar Market” website has contributed to the digital transformation of this process, allowing for continuation of purchases and sales transaction under equilibrium condition (Behar Market, n.d.; WTO, 2023). Information asymmetry is thus bridged and ensures that domestic and external entities obtain pricing data.

Al-Abri et al. (2009) research indicated that fish pricing in Oman markets demonstrates excellent resource efficiency when analyzed economically. The pricing system effectively represents operational costs since there are slight differences between the actual price and

the theoretical price, considering logistics and transportation (FAO, 2019). The ability to recognize species using their indigenous names and the freshness of the product are the critical qualitative factors impacting price (FAO, 2019). Additionally, market value increases due to increasing industry demand from fish meal and oil producers, who handle vast volumes of anchovies (MAFWR, 2024; MAFWR, 2023).

Furthermore, natural supply situations and seasonality are also very much linked to high price fluctuations. The effect of the monsoon winds (fall) that affect fishing in the Al-Wusta and Dhofar governorates leads to a reduced supply and hence an increased price rise throughout the summer season (MAFWR, 2024; Mishrif, 2024). Conversely, where there is a huge drop in prices due to increased production of catches by artisanal fishing fleets, prices become extremely low. Emperor fish and kingfish, for instance, have been sold in the market at the lowest prices of 2 rials per kilogram. Anchovies are sold at 500 baisa per kilogram (Al-Roya Newspaper, 2026). This is because 77% of total output is produced by artisanal fishing; therefore, prices are highly dependent on this (FAO, 2019; MAFWR, 2024).

Government Intervention

In order to ensure sustainability and avoid the exhaustion of natural resources, the Omani government acts extensively and strategically as an enforcing agency in the fisheries and aquaculture industry. To do this, the Ministry of Agriculture and Fisheries enforce stringent policies through the enactment of legislation, including Ministerial Decision 241/2022, which prohibits the fishing of abalone, as well as setting specific fishing seasons, in order to ensure that these remain available for reasonable prices in the local market (MAFWR, 2024; MAFWR, 2022). Also, temporary restrictions are imposed on certain types of fish exports, including grouper and kingfish (high valued variety dropped 28.5% in production) (FAO, 2019; MAFWR, 2024; MAFWR, 2025; MAFWR, MAF, 2014). Economically, there are several investment incentives offered by the government, including tax exemptions for up to 10 years, along with the usufruct system for land acquisition by aquaculture businesses. Through subsidies in fuel consumption and equipping the artisanal fleet with

modern technology such as sonar and Vessel Monitoring System (VMS), the government also aids in the reduction of production costs (MAFWR, 2024; Mishrif, 2024).

One government entity that has emerged as a significant player in moving towards the “blue economy” is the Oman Fisheries Development Company (FDO) (FDO, 2022) . To reduce dependence on imported products, this government organization ensures that there are companies that are dedicated to the localization of aquaculture technologies and feed substitutes (MCIIP, 2024). In essence, the government established the “Bahar” virtual auction website that played a critical role in improving price mechanisms between producers and consumers (WTO, 2023; Behar, n.d.).

Finding & Discussion

Statistics indicate that the development rate in Oman’s fisheries sector stood at 13.5% per annum, with production recorded at 900,630 tons in 2024. Market structure is characterized by a segmented market, where commercial and aquaculture fishery companies are mainly controlled by firms such as FDO and show oligopoly characteristics. While artisan fishery firms account for 60,000 fishermen and contribute 77% of production, using the perfect competition model. To enhance the fishing industry's efficiency and reduce expenses, the industry structure implies that firms have to improve their negotiating position through the use of innovative techniques like sonar stock location systems. This disparity calls for prudent regulation by the authorities to assist large corporations in meeting their goals of Oman Vision 2040 while at the same time balancing market dynamics and avoiding the marginalization of the local fisher men.

Regarding the pricing and logistics, empirical research reveals that the Omani fish market are characterized by an efficient transport network that charges prices reflecting the costs of transportation. The suppliers rational behavior leads to an emphasis on exports, which make up 37% of production to boost their profits. In such a situation, the domestic consumer faces a dilemma of balancing between equity and efficiency. Thus, the per capita consumption of fish will reduce, requiring policy changes in terms of ensuring food security through setting quotas for the domestic market or subsidizing popular varieties.

Moreover, the digitalization of the “Bahar” platform ensures greater price transparency and minimizes the risk of a market failure caused by lack of information.

As far as supply and demand dynamics are concerned, supply encounters major seasonal fluctuations with sharp reductions in the amount of production in summer because of the influence of the monsoon period (fall). These factors trigger cyclic price spikes. To deal with such an issue and ensure a stable flow throughout the whole year, firms make use of advanced storage and transportation methods, including freezing and refrigeration. The fish oil and fish meal industry, which consumed 223 thousand tons of anchovies in 2023, became a considerable industrial demand. This increases the industrial added value and puts further pressure on natural resources. Thus, it is essential to enact restrictions on fishing (Regulation 241/2022) (MAFWR, 2022).

In conclusion, localization of the fish feed industry is a key strategic move towards reducing dependency on imports that leave the industry vulnerable to disruptions in logistics and fluctuations in currency value. Reducing production costs of aquaculture firms, integration of factories such as the one located in Khazaen Economic City reduces costs for manufacturers, allowing their products to remain competitive both locally and regionally. In spite of the variations in traditional fishing seasons, this industry is able to provide customers with a steady source of protein alternatives at affordable prices. Investment incentives provided by the government will continue to be necessary to attract quality investors to the industry.

Policy Recommendations

To increase the sustainability and competitiveness of Oman's fishing and aquaculture sectors, the following policy recommendations are made:

- The first solution suggested herein is the need for improved regional cold chain logistics and storage facilities. This proposal is consistent with studies showing that there was a strong supply shock witnessed in July, where there was a drop in deliveries by 43.6% caused by adverse weather and monsoons (Mishrif, 2024;

MAFWR, 2024). Additionally, according to the resilience analysis in 2024, consumer consumption is highly elastic in response to availability supply since an increase in consumption of 17.7% was registered while prices were stable (MAFWR, 2024). As a result, it can be recommended that the government invest in more efficient collection and refrigeration centres in remote governorates such as Al Wusta and Dhofar to manage the surplus and distribute it during periods of scarcity. The downside to maintaining consistent prices throughout the year is the high-cost requirements imposed by the government. In the short run, this would mean reduced profit opportunities for intermediary parties making profits based on price hikes during supply scarcity.

- The second measure suggested involves adaptive management of fishing licenses and quotas based on research findings that show the considerable strain on highly valued fish species, like kingfish. There has been a significant decline in kingfish catch by 28.5%, although the average price has gone up. This clearly reflects that the stock has been fully exploited at present. It has become necessary to apply the concept of flexible fishing licenses in accordance with the prevailing stock situation along with export quotas for endangered species, in order to conserve the environment. The economic cost involved includes a decrease in the revenue generated by an entire segment of the population consisting of 63,259 artisanal fishers, who depend upon exports for better remuneration than the local market.
- Recommendation three is to enhance the value chain of the locality through increasing the localization of aquatic feed innovation and production. It was found that the aquaculture industry operates under high capital-intensive nature and is very vulnerable to import feed price volatility, which leads to increased cost levels. Based on the previous interventions made by the government, where it opened a feed mill in Khazaen Economic City for 36 million rials, further tax breaks can be provided to companies that apply innovations in recycling local agricultural waste and using it as an input to develop high- quality feed. On the other hand,

compulsory use of the local feed will make the price of the product much higher compared to its competitors from international producers who produce their feed based on imports.

Conclusion

In summary, this research proves that there is a strategic change in the Omani fisheries sector in terms of achieving the best performance. In 2024, the sector produced 900,630 tons with a value of 580 million Omani rials. The high effectiveness is achieved through the successful implementation of a dual market structure that combines the artisanal fishing sector that controls 77% of all landings, along with systematic development of the FDO in commercial fishing and aquaculture for increasing added value.

The relevance of the research from the point of view of scientific knowledge includes the creation of the practical model of application of the concept of market efficiency versus distributive equity. The study showed that the extremely effective transportation and marketing structure of Oman logically encourages suppliers to sell their products abroad to obtain maximum profit. Therefore, this creates a threat to national food security. Moreover, the research provides the data for determining the price elasticity of demand since the Arc Elasticity calculated shows that Omani consumers have elastic demand in regard to decreasing prices, which led to an increase in per capita annual consumption.

For the standpoint of practice and policy making, the most important results of this research include the identification of supply shocks in July when it dropped by 43.6% because of weather factors. Therefore, measures such as regional cold chains and the provision of flexible licenses can be used to maintain supply-demand equilibrium. Moreover, the shift towards localization of aquaculture feed production in Khazaen region will be helpful for reducing expenses and protecting aquaculture companies from global exchange rate risks.

In conclusion, the research proved that according to the plans of Oman Vision 2040, further development of the sector can be achieved through transferring from mere extraction of natural resources to the sustainable food industry involving digital innovations and advanced aquaculture technology.

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